

Observation of Itinerant antiferromagnetism in Y-substituted CeNiGe₂

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We investigate the results of magnetization and resistivity studies on Y substituted heavy fermionic system CeNiGe₂. Investigations are carried out on the compounds CeNiGe₂, Ce_{0.9}Y_{0.1}NiGe₂, Ce_{0.8}Y_{0.2}NiGe₂ and Ce_{0.6}Y_{0.4}NiGe₂. In CeNiGe₂, it is observed that a fraction of delocalized spin coexists with localized spins. With the increase Y concentration, the antiferromagnetic transition temperature decreases while itinerant moments increases. It is also noted that resistivity increases across the series. This observation points that with the increase in Y-substitution, the decrease of resistivity below ordering temperature is suppressed indicating that the itinerancy increases leading to enhanced scattering. Thus site dilution of Ce results in the observation of itinerant antiferromagnetic behavior in these compounds.

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